

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

Association of Methylenetetrahydrofolate Reductase (*MTHFR*) Gene C677T (rs1801133) polymorphism among Sudanese patients with chronic myelogenous leukemia

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Abstract

Background: Methylenetetrahydrofolate reductase (*MTHFR*) is a key enzyme regulating the intracellular folate metabolism which plays an important role in carcinogenesis through DNA methylation.

Objectives: The current study aimed to determine the association between *MTHFR* C677T polymorphisms and the risks of chronic myeloid leukemia (CML).

Material and methods: This are hospital based cross sectional case control study, a total of 170 Sudanese subjects were enrolled, and 75 patients with chronic myeloid leukemia and 75 age- and sex matched healthy volunteers as a control group. Genomic DNA was extracted by sodium chloride method and The SNPs genotypes were determined using polymerase chain reaction followed by restriction fragment length polymorphism method. (PCR- RFLP). Data of this study were collected using a structured interview questionnaire and analyzed by statistical package for social sciences (version 21).

Results: The frequency of the CC genotype was higher in the control group compared with patients (100%,96%), while of the CT genotype was higher in the case (4%) than in control (0.0%); the TT genotype was absent in both study groups, the frequencies T and C allele were 0.02 and 0.98 in CML patient group and 0.00, 0.100 respectively in the control group. There was no clinically significant association between age (P.value= 0.3), gender (P.value= 0.4) and genotype, also there was no statistically significant association when compare case with control genotype (p. value 0.08).

Conclusion: C677T *MTHFR* polymorphism is not associated with the risk of CML among the Sudanese population

Keywords: Leukemia; Methylenetetrahydrofolate reductase; Polymorphism; Sudan

1. Introduction

CML is a myeloproliferative malignancy characterized by accumulation of myeloid precursors in bone marrow, peripheral blood and body tissues [1]. Studies have shown that 95% of patients with CML possess the Philadelphia chromosome which results from a reciprocal translocation t(9;22)(q31;q11) between chromosome 9 and chromosome 22. The translocation results in the formation of a fusion gene that encodes Bcr Abl protein, which possesses aberrant protein tyrosine kinase activity. This, in turn, activates its downstream signaling pathways involving cell proliferation,

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metastasis, cell survival, and differentiation. Progression of CML patients is divided into three phases, namely chronic phase, accelerated phase and blast crisis phase. CML patients with no treatment will develop fatal blast crisis phase within 5 years [2,3,4,5]. Although the biological and clinical aspects of CML have been well documented, little is known about the mechanism underlying the genesis of Philadelphia chromosome and the factors influencing individuals' susceptibility to CML. To date, there have been no reports on familial, geographic, hereditary, ethnic and economic association with the pathogenesis of CML, and the mechanisms behind the disease progression haven't been fully understood as well [6]. It is recognized that leukemia is derived from abnormally proliferating hematopoietic tissue with greatest DNA synthesis, and thought the pathogenesis of CML would be associated with the metabolic fate of folic acid [7]. Methylene Tetrahydrofolate Reductase (MTHFR) is the rate-limiting enzyme in the methyl cycle, and it is encoded by the MTHFR gene [8,9]. The MTHFR gene is located on the short (p) arm of chromosome 1 at position 36.3 [9]. It spans approximately 2.2Kb and consist of 11 exons [10]. MTHFR enzyme is composed of an N-terminal catalytic domain and a C-terminal regulatory domain. MTHFR has at least two promoters and two isoforms (70 k Da and 77 k Da) [11]. Methylene tetrahydrofolate reductase catalyzes the conversion of 5, 10-methylenetetrahydrofolate to 5-methyltetrahydrofolate, a co-substrate for homocysteine re-methylation to methionine [12]. The (C677T, rs1801133) polymorphisms in MTHFR gene have been described: First, C to T transition at nucleotide 677 (C677T, rs1801133), which causes the substitution alanine with valine at codon 222, and decreases in the enzymatic activity, and subsequently increases the level of homocysteine and altered distribution of folate [13]. The mutant gene produces an inactive enzyme that has been associated with uracil misincorporation into DNA, DNA double strand breaks during uracil excision repair, thus increasing the risk of chromosomal aberrations and malignancy [14].

2. Methodology

This is an analytical case-control study, conducted at Khartoum state, Sudan, in the period from July 2017 to July 2022. In which, 75 patients were confirmed diagnosis of CML and 75 age- and sex-matched apparently healthy volunteers- as a control group- were enrolled. Venous blood samples were collected from all participants in Ethylenediamine tetra acetic acid (EDTA). Genomic DNA was isolated from peripheral leucocytes manually by using sodium chloride method and stored at -30°C until PCR is carried out. MTHFR C677T polymorphism was analyzed by Allele-Specific Polymerase Chain Reaction (AS-PCR) followed by restriction enzyme. A reaction mixture of 20µl was prepared for each sample, containing 5µl genomic DNA, 1µL of each of the forward (5'GCAAGTCCCCAAGGAGG-3'), reverse (5'GGTCCCCACTTCCAGCAT-3'), (Rabab M Aly et al; 2014) (MACROGEN, KOREA), 5µL master mix (MAXIME PCR PRE-MIX KIT (I-TAQ), INTRON, KOREA), and 8µL sterile distilled water. The amplification program consists of initial denaturation at 95°C for 5 minutes; then 40 cycles [each consists of denaturation at 95°C for 30 second, annealing at 60°C for 1 minutes, and extension at 72°C for 1minutes], and a final extension at 72°C for 7 minutes. PCR products were incubated over night with HINF restriction enzyme (restriction enzyme was prepared by 7.5 µl of DW, 2 µl of enzyme buffer and 0.5 µl of enzyme) then the product was separated on 3% agarose gel electrophoresis containing ethidium bromide with a 100 bp DNA ladder (SOLIS BIODYEN, ESTONIA) run with each batch of samples and the size of the fragments was determined under UV transilluminator (SYNGENE, JAPAN). A PCR fragment of 175 bp, 23bp, indicates the presence TT genotype, while a fragment of 175, 198 bp and 23bp indicates to CT genotype and the wild type (CC state) remains undigested, preserving the original 198 bp fragment.

Patient's data were collected using a structured interview questionnaire and analyzed by statistical package for social science (SPSS), version 21. The qualitative data were presented as frequency and percentage. Quantitative data were presented as Mean±SD. Association between qualitative variable was tested by Chi-square (X²) and Fisher's exact tests. Multivariate logistic regression analysis was used for the examination of interaction between the polymorphism and MI risk factors. The allele frequency and Hardy Weinberg Equilibrium (HWE) were calculated using the conventional formulas.

The study was approved by the scientific research committee, faculty of medical laboratory sciences, Karary University Khartoum, Sudan.

3. Results

A total of 150 Sudanese subjects were enrolled in this study, 75 patients with chronic myeloid leukemia, and 75 healthy volunteers as a control group. The patients' and control age were ranged from 20 to 70 years (44.5 ± 16.1) and age of the controls was ranged from 29 to 70 years (38.5 ± 12.1) with no previous history and risk factor of CML as shown in (Table 1), the patients age divided as group, (20-30y) (37%), (31-40) (43%), (41-50) (33%), (51-60) (24%) and more than (60y) (13%) as shown in (Figure 3.1), forty three (57%) of patients were male and thirty two (43%) were female in comparison to control, male were forty four (59%) and other part (41%) were female, the most common sign of

patients was Splenomegaly (48%), fatigability (43%), fever (33%) huge Splenomegaly (31%) and abdominal pain (25%) as shown in (Figure 2). According to genotype, the analysis of result showed that For C677T polymorphism, the results of PCR amplification yielded one amplicons, length 198 bp and Post digestion documentation was done on gel electrophoresis, the results yielded 198bp indicate CC genotype, 198, 175 and 23bp for CT genotype nobody with TT genotype were found in both patient and control groups as shown in (Figure 3). There was no clinically significant association between age ($P.value= 0.3$) as in (Table 2), gender ($P.value= 0.4$) as in (Table 3) and genotype, there was no statistically significant association when compare patients with control genotype ($p. value 0.08$) as shown in (Table 4). The distribution of allele frequency within each group in Hardy-Weinberg equilibrium was found, the prevalence of the C allele was 0.98 in the patients and 100 % in the control group, where T allele was 0.02 in patients and 0.00 in control group as shown in (Table 5). This indicates no a significant association of the T allele with CML patients in contrast to control. No statistically significant association was observed between the C677T MTHFR polymorphism and CML risk and this variant may not be a genetic risk factor for CML susceptibility in Sudan.

Table 1 Characteristic of patient and control

Characteristic	Patients	Control
N	75	75
Age	44.5 ± 16.1	38.5 ± 12.1
Sex(male: female)	43:32	44:31

Figure 1 PCR-base restriction analysis of MTHFR C677T polymorphism shown on 3% agarose electrophoresis. The polymorphic region was amplified by PCR resulting in digestible fragment length 198 bp indicated for CC genotype in lane 1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8, L: ladder, 100 bp ladder (Fermentas, Germany).

Figure 2 Age group of patients

Figure 3 Frequency of sign and symptoms among patients

Table 2 Comparison between patient’s genotype and age group

Hinf		Age					P.value
		20-30	31-40	41-50	51-60	> 60	
CC	Count	13	18	16	13	12	0.3
	%	100.0%	94.7%	88.9%	100.0%	100.0%	
CT	Count	0	1	2	0	0	
	%	0.0%	5.3%	11.1%	0.0%	0.0%	
Total	Count	13	19	18	13	12	
	%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	

Table 3 Comparison between patient’s genotype and gender

Hinf		Gender		P. value
		male	Female	
CC	Count	42	30	0.4
	%	97.7%	93.8%	
CT	Count	1	2	
	%	2.3%	6.3%	
Total	Count	43	32	
	%	100.0%	100.0%	

Figure 4 Frequency of genotype in patients and control

Table 4 Comparison between patients and control genotype

Hinf		Sample		Total	P. value
		Case	control		
CC	Count	72	75	147	0.08
	%	96.0%	100.0%	98.0%	
CT	Count	3	0	3	
	%	4.0%	0.0%	2.0%	
Total	Count	75	75	150	
	%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	

Table 5 T and C allele Frequency

MTHFR(C677T)	Patients	Control
C	0.98	100
T	0.02	0.0

4. Discussion

This a case control study was conducted to investigate the association of methylene tetra hydro folate reductase enzyme polymorphism C677T among Sudanese patients with chronic myeloid leukemia confirmed. This study was carried on 150 Sudanese individual, seventy five apparent healthy as control and seventy five as CML, forty three of patients were male and thirty two were female, forty four of control were male and Thirty one were female. The result of current study showed there was no clinically significant association between age ($P.value= 0.3$), gender ($P.value= 0.4$) and genotype and this agree with Rabab M Aly et al in 2014 no statistical difference for age when compared CML patients with genotype [15]in addition revealed that there was no difference for sex distribution in respect to C677T genotype and this completely agree with the current study in contrary Lordelo in 2012 et al that the C677T more associated with male than female [16] regarding the allele and genotype frequency, the CC genotype was more in control group than patients (100%, 96%) respectively and the CT was more common in patients than control (4%, 0.0%) respectively with no significance difference when compare them ($P.value= 0.08$), this agree with Rabab M Aly et al in 2014 The frequency

of the MTHFR 677CC genotype was higher among controls (45.0%) when compared to CML patients (35.2%). In addition, for CML patients, the frequency of the 677CT genotype (51.7%) was higher than control group (49.0%) but with no statistical significance ($P = 0.981$) also Lordelo in 2012 revealed that CC genotype more common in control than patients and this similar with the finding of present study in contrast to the current study was showed CT also more common in control[16]. The present study finding which showed there was no association between C677T polymorphism and risk for CML seemed to contradict Rabab M Aly et al in 2014 an association between MTHFR polymorphisms (677TT) and risk of developing CML, also Barbosa and his colleagues did not find any significant association between both MTHFR polymorphisms and CML[17] in addition Lordelo showed that there was no association between C677T and CML patients (Lordelo et al; 2012) and Pazhakh Vahid also agree with the present study which found that the polymorphism do not contribute to an inherited genetic susceptibility of CML [18,19], while Robin *et al.* who investigated the relationship between MTHFR polymorphisms and the risk of relapse after hematopoietic cell transplantation for CML, observed a decrease in the relapse risk of patients with variants of both MTHFR polymorphisms [20] also in study performed in Jordan by Ismail said in 2009 there result conflict with present study which showed that a significant association of c677T with CML risk [21].

5. Conclusion

The homozygous C/C genotype was more frequent in the patient and the healthy controls, while the T/T genotype was completely absent in both study groups. However, there was no statistically significant association between MTHFR C1677T polymorphism and risk of CML among the Sudanese population.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

There was no conflict of interest in this study. Statement of informed consent Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study.

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